

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES

Scientific and Academy Journal

Print ISSN 2222-7288

Online ISSN 2518-5551

IMPACT FACTOR VALUE OF 2.329

Vol. (46/2)–SPECIAL ISSUE JULY-2025

**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE**

**5. Vital Security Paradigm in the New
Millennium: Coordinate System and State-of-
the-Art. By IGOR RYZHOV and others. p. 94.**

CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH-DENMARK

AALBORG ACADEMY OF SCIENCES – DENMARK

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JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

P.ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

VOL. 45-2-ISSUE 3-June 2025 -Special issue

JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES

SCIENTIFIC AND ACADEMY JOURNAL

Print ISSN 2222-7288

Online ISSN 2518-5551

IMPACT FACTOR VALUE OF 2.701

VOL. (46/2) SPECIAL ISSUE JULY 2025

FIRST EDITION 2011

SPECIAL ISSUE

**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE
A GROUP OF UNIVERSITY GRADUATES IN UKRAINE
PREPARED**

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FACULTY OF LAW - ACADEMY OF THE AALBORG – DENMARK**

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VOL. 45-2-ISSUE 3-June 2025 -Special issue

First edition 2011

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JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

P.ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

First edition 2011

IMPACT FACTOR 2.329

VOL. 45-2-ISSUE 3-June 2025 -Special issue

The Journal certified by:

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<p>The Journal of Law and Political Sciences is published by the Law and Political Research Center which is accredited by CVR - Det Centrale Virksomhedsregister-Denmark</p>	 cvr virk
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JOURNAL OF LAW AND POLITICAL SCIENCES (JLPS)

P.ISSN 2222-7288 E. ISSN 2518-5551

IMPACT FACTOR 2.329

VOL. 45-2-ISSUE 3-June 2025 -Special issue

First edition 2011

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Editor ICR Team (ISD) International Scientific Indexing (ISI)

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(5)

VITAL SECURITY PARADIGM IN NEW MILLENNIUM: COORDINATE SYSTEM AND STATE-OF-THE-ART

Receipt 21May

Approval 30 June

Publishing July 2025

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ABSTRACT

The relevance of the study is due to the aggravation of the problem of ensuring a safe and dignified human existence in the 21st century, which is significantly intensified under the influence of new global challenges, dangers and threats. The modern international community together with national states have not yet developed sufficient and effective programs to address these challenges. In this context, the issue of ensuring the security of the individual, the so-called “security of vital activity”, which is aimed at protecting his vital interests in the light of the constant emergence of new threats and dangers, is particularly important. This necessitates the search for innovative and adaptive approaches to effectively protect a person in the conditions of a dynamic hybrid world. The purpose of this study is to systematize existing knowledge in the field of personal security and conceptualize effective measures to ensure it in the conditions of modern hybrid challenges. The result was the formulation of a new vision of vital security, adapted to the realities of the era of hybridity, in particular the phenomenon of the hybrid world, which is characterized by multi-level interactions, competition and cooperation. The novelty of the study lies in the development of a unique LEGO-model of the “pyramid” of life security, which logically reflects its components and interrelationships. The paper analyzes the shortcomings of both realistic and neorealistic concepts of the liberal world, which do not fully take into account local features and the multifaceted nature of human security. In view of this, there is an urgent need to improve the paradigm of life

security, which takes into account constant changes in the conditions of a hybrid world and allows us to adequately respond to the complex multi-problem challenges of our time.

Keywords: human security, life safety, armed conflicts, hybrid threats, socio-psychological security.

1- INTRODUCTION

Since the mid-1990s, the idea of human vulnerability has increasingly been heard in scientific and expert discussions on new approaches to security. It has gradually acquired the status of one of the central concepts in the concept of modern security^{1, 2, 3}. More than thirty years have passed, and today human security is no longer perceived as a secondary element – on the contrary, it has become a cornerstone in political, economic, social and humanitarian research^{4, 5}. This is due to the generally recognized truth: security is not only a basic need, but also a fundamental value on which human dignity, development and well-being depend. In a world experiencing constant crises – from military conflicts to environmental disasters and cyber threats – human security has acquired critical importance. It is the foundation of the resilience not only of individual communities, but also of entire states and regions⁶. At the same time, despite this obvious importance, most national security strategies still do not pay due attention to the human dimension of security. The main emphasis continues to be placed on military power, territorial integrity and state interests, leaving the needs of the

¹ Human Security (2014). In: C. B. Field, V. R. Barros, D. J. Dokken, K. J. Mach, & M. D. Mastrandrea (Eds.), *Climate Change 2014 Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability*. (pp. 755–792). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9781107415379.017>

² MDUK (2024). JSP 985 Human Security in Defence. Ministry of Defence of the United Kingdom. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/668d2b5fab5fc5929851bc2c/JSP_985.pdf

³ CSDP (2025). The Common Security and Defence Policy. [https://www.european-cyber-defence-policy.com/Common_Security_Defence_Policy_\(CSDP\).html](https://www.european-cyber-defence-policy.com/Common_Security_Defence_Policy_(CSDP).html)

⁴ Gómez, O. A., & Gasper, D. (2022). The Position of Crisis in Human Development Processes and Thinking: Using the Human Security Perspective in an Era of Transitions. *UNDP Special Report on Human Security*. <https://hdr.undp.org/system/files/documents/background-paper-document/2022hsrgomezgasper.pdf>

⁵ Mine, Y., Miyahara, C., Muto, A., Saito, Y., Takeuchi, K., & Kajino, M. (2024). Politics and Society under Compounded Crises. JICA Ogata Research Institute Report Human Security Today Human Security. No. 2. https://www.jica.go.jp/Resource/jica-ri/publication/booksandreports/jveaq800000071xq-att/Human_Security_Today_EN_20221031.pdf

⁶ WEF (2025b). Global Risks 2025: A world of growing divisions. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/global-risks-report-2025/in-full/global-risks-2025-a-world-of-growing-divisions-c943fe3ba0/>

individual vulnerable and often ignored⁷. Rethinking approaches to security in the 21st century involves recognizing that true security begins not with borders and armies, but with the security of each person – in their home, community, daily life⁸.

In recent decades, the concept of human security has become a real breakthrough in the field of international relations theory. In response to the growing challenges associated with inequality, poverty, environmental threats and humanitarian crises, the idea of human security offers a new orientation: it puts the person himself at the center of attention – his life, health, freedom and well-being, expanding the boundaries of the security paradigm far beyond the framework of state sovereignty and military defense⁹,¹⁰. This approach directly challenges established paradigms, in particular realism and neorealism, that have dominated international relations theory for a long time. Instead of state competition and hegemony, the human security paradigm emphasizes the interpersonal dimension of security, solidarity, and humanitarian principles¹¹. However, in a world where threats are increasingly hybrid, non-classical in nature, it is precisely a humanitarian-oriented approach to security that has every chance of becoming the basis for a rethinking of the global order and international coexistence.

Social crises, in particular war, are indicators of the vulnerability of modern society, exposing systemic shortcomings in the institutional, moral and security spheres. In such conditions, the course of conflicts is largely determined by the ability of the national security system – as a complex of state institutions and the civil sector – to respond effectively to external and internal threats, ensuring the protection of basic rights and freedoms of citizens, as well as their personal capacity for moral, psychological and physical resilience¹².

Modern armed confrontations and terrorist threats demonstrate the blurring of the legal and moral boundaries of war: targeted attacks on civilian infrastructure such as schools and hospitals, remote assassinations, the use of toxic substances, sexual

⁷ Idachaba, E. U. (2019). Military-Focused Security. In: Romaniuk, S., Thapa, M., Marton, P. (Eds.), *The Palgrave Encyclopedia of Global Security Studies*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-74336-3_85-1

⁸ Jacobs, G. (2016). Integrated Approach to Peace & Human Security in the 21st Century. *CADMUS*, 5(3), Part 2, 49–71. Retrieved from <https://www.cadmusjournal.org/files/pdfreprints/vol3issue1/cadmus-v3-i1-peace-human-security-gjacobs-reprint.pdf>

⁹ Skulysh, Ye. (2023). Evolution of the concept of human security in international legal discourse. *Scientific works of the Interregional Academy of Personnel Management. Legal Sciences*, 2(62), 65–70. <https://doi.org/10.32689/2522-4603.2022.2.10>

¹⁰ Vejnović, D., & Obrenović, P. (2023). Human Security in Traditional Security Theories- Challenges and Perspectives. In: *Strategic Intersections: The New Architecture of International Security*. (pp. 243–255). University of Belgrade. https://doi.org/10.18485/isimod_strint.2023.ch15

¹¹ Sotirović, V. (2025). Human Security and its Dimensions. Centre for Geostrategic Studies in Belgrade, Serbia. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/388560043_Human_Security_and_its_Dimensions

¹² Emergency, S. (2004). Societal Security and Crisis Management in the 21st Century. CRN-Workshop Report Stockholm, Sweden, https://css.ethz.ch/content/dam/ethz/special-interest/gess/cis/center-for-securities-studies/pdfs/Report_CRN_Stockholm.pdf

violence and massive violations of humanitarian law have become a brutal reality. The result is massive forced displacement and the destruction of social order^{13, 14}.

In these circumstances, the concept of vital security is undergoing a profound transformation. Its study is becoming critically important for the development of effective state policies and strategies in response to dynamic challenges and new, often hybrid threats – both at the level of individual states and on a global scale^{15, 16}.

The theoretical and applied rethinking of the concept of human security implies a new vision of its reference object, focusing exclusively on the human being as a subject and object of protection. In modern conditions, vital security should be integrated into a multidimensional national security system, acquiring the features of an autonomous subsystem with clearly defined priorities.

The purpose of this publication is to systematize current knowledge in the field of personal security and develop effective tools to ensure it as a key element of the overall strategy of human resilience in an unstable world.

Literature review

Despite the growing attention to the concept of human security, there is still no universally accepted definition. Different actors – international organizations, governments, academia, non-governmental organizations, and the private sector – have developed their own approaches to the concept, leading to its broad and often ambiguous interpretation¹⁷. This complicates the practical application of the concept, particularly in issues of the legitimacy of external intervention under the pretext of human protection. In contemporary literature, human security is viewed as an interdisciplinary concept that combines human rights, development, and humanitarian security. It is interpreted not only as an analytical framework, but also as a potential political strategy that rethinks the classical security paradigm¹⁸. The central tenet of this concept is to shift the emphasis from a state-centric vision of security to the person –

¹³ Gross, M. L. (2010). *Moral Dilemmas of Modern War. Torture, Assassination, and Blackmail in an Age of Asymmetric Conflict*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511811562>

¹⁴ Levchenko, A. (2023). Needs in the healthcare system are growing due to the war – Head of the WHO Office in Ukraine. *Interfax-Ukraine*. <https://interfax.com.ua/news/interview/946050.html>

¹⁵ Costigan, S. S., & Hennessy, M. A. (2024). Hybrid threats and hybrid warfare reference curriculum. NATO Headquarters Brussels, June 2024. https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/2024/7/pdf/241007-hybrid-threats-and-hybrid-warfare.pdf

¹⁶ Sott, M. K., & Bender, M. S. (2025). The Role of Adaptive Leadership in Times of Crisis: A Systematic Review and Conceptual Framework. *Merits*, 5(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.3390/merits5010002>

¹⁷ Eshghi, S. (2024). The concept of Human Security. *Heinrich Böll Stiftung*. <https://www.boell.de/en/2024/05/21/concept-human-security>

¹⁸ UNTFHS (2024). General Assembly Informal Plenary Meeting on the Report of the Secretary-General (A/78/665). United Nations Trust Fund for Human Security. https://www.un.org/humansecurity/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Summary_Informal-Meeting-of-the-General-Assembly-on-Human-Security_2-April-2024.pdf

their rights, dignity, and living conditions¹⁹. This approach responds to contemporary challenges, including rising inequality, instability, new forms of armed conflict²⁰, and global crises, including pandemics and climate change.

Recent initiatives, such as “Human Security for All” (2022–2024), aim to raise global awareness and acceptance of the concept of human security as a universal and effective framework for policies and programs in a world facing complex crises and accelerating megatrends²¹.

One of the simplest yet most profound definitions of security is the absence of fear and threats. A sense of security means not only protection from physical, sexual or psychological violence, persecution or death, but also freedom from basic deprivation such as hunger, unemployment or lack of medical care. In this context, human security includes identifying potential threats, preventing them from occurring, and minimizing harm if the danger cannot be avoided²².

This approach focuses not only on protecting people from direct physical threats, but also on creating a sustainable environment where access to basic life resources, social protection and support is ensured. This is particularly important in the context of crises caused by war, human rights violations, or deep social inequalities that undermine basic livelihoods²³.

Thus, the broadened interpretation of security combines two key ideas: first, it goes beyond a narrowly military understanding to include aspects of everyday human life; second, it emphasizes the importance of creating social safety nets that can support people in times of instability and uncertainty.

As Ahmadzai²⁴ rightly notes, the concept of human security is interdisciplinary and multidimensional, as its focus is shifted from the state to the individual as the main unit of analysis. Unlike traditional paradigms, human security covers a range of threats that directly affect the lives, well-being and dignity of people on a global scale. This approach has emerged as a new security paradigm in the post-bipolar world, after the end of the Cold War, and offers tools for a deeper understanding of the challenges faced by modern societies.

¹⁹ Gómez, O. A., & Gasper, D. (2022). *Id.*

²⁰ Barbieri, M., & Aleksanyan, N. (2024). Human Security as a Factor of Sustainable Security in Post-War Armenia. *Journal of Political Science: Bulletin of Yerevan University*, 3, 2(8), 42–64. <https://doi.org/10.46991/JOPS/2024.3.8.042>

²¹ HS4A (2025). The Human Security For All Campaign: Progress Report October 2022 – March 2024. Human Security for All. <https://humansecurity.world/progress-report/>

²² Muguruza, Ch. (2007). Human Security as a policy framework: Critics and challenges. *Yearbook on Humanitarian Action and Human Rights*, 4, 15–35.

²³ Tadjbakhsh, Sh. (2005). Human security: Concepts and implications (with an application to post-intervention challenges in Afghanistan). *Les Etudes du CERI*, 117-118, 1–77.

²⁴ Ahmadzai, A. (2020). Local knowledge on development: The missing link in the research-policy nexus of sustainable development. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 13(2), 132–147. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jsd.v13n2p132>

In the structure of human security, an important place is occupied by vital security, a concept that puts people, and their physical, social and environmental well-being, at the center of protection, rather than the state²⁵. Proponents of this approach emphasize that phenomena such as poverty, hunger, epidemics, forced displacement, social exclusion, and environmental degradation are no less destructive than wars or terrorist acts²⁶. They believe that development, peace, human rights, and security are interconnected and should be viewed as interdependent aspects of global well-being.

The academic debate on the essence of human security is divided between two approaches: The “broad” approach, which emphasizes freedom from want (i.e., developmental focus), and the “narrow” approach, which focuses on freedom from fear (i.e., human rights protection). Both vectors interpret human security as a response to the changing nature of threats in a globalized world.

Since the end of the Cold War, the idea of human security has gained widespread support, gradually integrating into the mainstream of international relations. However, against this background, there is considerable criticism from representatives of the realist school. In their view, the security of the state will always prevail over the needs of individuals if these needs do not coincide with national interests. According to Schütte and Fordelone²⁷, in the realities of power politics, human rights often remain on the periphery of decisions.

This point of view is reflected in the criticism of the neoconservative course of the Bush administration by realist conservatives in the United States. The policy of strategic exportation of liberal democracy, in particular through military intervention in Iraq, has been strongly opposed by leading realists. For example, according to Toft²⁸, the idea that the fight against terror should be accompanied by the global spread of democracy seems overly idealistic. In turn, Walt and Mearsheimer²⁹ argued that the war in Iraq was a strategic mistake – not timely and in the wrong geographical location, diverting resources from fighting real threats.

The Human Security paradigm poses a serious challenge to traditional approaches to security based on the hegemony of realism and neorealism. Modern studies show that the inclusion of this approach in foreign policy does not contradict national interests, but rather depends on how these interests are interpreted in the political and normative context³⁰. In the case of the European Union, the concept of human security has actually

²⁵ Gebre, G. (2015). *Philosophical discourse on human security: Re-conceptualisation of the new security paradigm in Africa*. LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing.

²⁶ Singh, J. (2016). Human security: A theoretical analysis. *Prime Scholars Library*, 4(3), 33–37.

²⁷ Schütte, R., & Fordelone, T. (2006). Human Security: a paradigm contradicting the national interest? *Carta Internacional*, Julho, 1(2), 35–40. <https://cartainternacional.abri.org.br/Carta/article/view/390>

²⁸ Toft, P. (2005). John J. Mearsheimer: An offensive realist between geopolitics and power. *Journal of International Relations and Development*, 8, 381–408. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.jird.1800065>

²⁹ Walt, J., & Mearsheimer, S. (2008). *The Israel lobby and U.S. foreign policy*. Farrar, Straus and Giroux.

³⁰ Hanlon, R., & Christie, K. (2016). *Freedom from fear, freedom from want: An introduction to human security*. University of Toronto Press. <https://doi.org/10.3138/9781442609594>

become a basic component of foreign policy practice. Therefore, overcoming the perceived contradiction between human security and national interests is of key importance.

Gaspar and Gómez³¹ emphasize the importance of “personal security” as a critical element in human security thinking and practice. It cannot be reduced to physical protection alone, but encompasses threats to basic needs and rights. The authors examine how UNDP reports and regional studies are increasingly focusing on women's security, property risks, and the broader social and structural factors that affect everyday life. This approach allows not only to complement the classical vision of security, but also to expand its humanitarian and human rights dimension.

The case of Ukraine shows how human security functions in the face of non-standard threats. Asmussen³² analyzes the impact of the 2014 Ukrainian crisis on international conflict resolution practice in the context of hybrid wars and the participation of unrecognized actors. The author emphasizes that in conditions when key actors are not part of international structures, the issue of human security becomes particularly complex. At the same time, the crisis has led to the strengthening of the OSCE's role as a platform for peaceful dialogue, which is a step towards the formation of a new European security system focused on people.

Environmental security is also increasingly seen as an integral part of human security. Khawas³³ emphasizes that environmental degradation, land degradation, water scarcity, and climate change can all directly or indirectly cause violence, migration, epidemics, and increased social tensions. Adger et al.³⁴ point out that climate change has the potential to exacerbate global crises by provoking competition for resources, destabilizing states, and exacerbating humanitarian disasters. However, as Gan³⁵ emphasizes, environmental cooperation also has the potential to unite – addressing common problems can not only reduce risks, but also build trust and promote long-term peace.

Societal challenges are becoming more diverse, and their connection to human security is growing in the face of scientific and technological progress. Unequal access to the latest technologies can cause “future shock” in communities that fail to adapt to changes in the global information environment. This creates risks of new isolation and

³¹ Gómez, O. A., & Gaspar, D. (2022). *Id.*

³² Asmussen, J. (2014). International crisis management and human security in the framework of 'hybrid wars' and unrecognised states. *Security and Human Rights*, 25(3), 287–297. <https://doi.org/10.1163/18750230-02503001>

³³ Khawas, V. (2014). Environmental challenges and issues of human security in Eastern Nepal. *The Himalayan Miscellany*, 25, 30–60.

³⁴ Adger, W., de Campos, R., Siddiqui, T., Gavonell, M., Szaboova, L., Rocky, M., Bhuiyan, M., & Billah, T. (2021). Human security of urban migrant populations affected by length of residence and environmental hazards. *Journal of Peace Research*, 58(1), 50–66. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022343320973717>

³⁵ Gan, N. (2024). *Climate change and threats to human security*. Kalpaz Publications.

forms of crime, including cybercrime^{36, 37}. At the same time, gender transformations in patriarchal societies – although accompanied by conflicts – can signal deeper shifts towards social progress³⁸.

Krause³⁹ emphasizes that since 1994, personal security has become an important component of security sector and foreign policy reforms. However, as he notes, other aspects of human security, such as health or food security, remain marginalized. In European and North American approaches, the emphasis tends to be on deterring physical violence.

Individualized approaches focused on human security shift the focus to emotional, psychological and subjective aspects, which has broadened the understanding of the nature of threats. This emphasizes the importance of “framing”, i.e., perceiving and understanding it as a critical factor in shaping a safe environment. In particular, UN Women's research⁴⁰ shows that in conflict-affected countries, priorities often shift from social needs to defense. For example, in 2019, Afghanistan spent 24% of its budget on defense and only 6% on health, 9% on education, and 4% on social protection.

Given the interconnectedness of social, economic, and environmental threats, attempts to divide human security into separate sectors are conditional and limited. Effective responses to such challenges require flexible, interdisciplinary solutions that take into account the complexity of “socio-environmental” systems. Birch⁴¹ notes that NATO's Strategic Concept 2022 reflects a new reality – increased competition, the threat of war in Europe, and a broader approach to security. Terrorism remains one of the main challenges, which the Alliance identifies as the most serious asymmetric threat. For the first time, this document clearly emphasizes the importance of human security and the Women, Peace and Security program⁴². NATO sees the challenge as integrating

³⁶ Estrada-Tanck, D. (2016). *Human security and human rights under international law: The protections offered to persons confronting structural vulnerability*. Hart.

³⁷ Shen, G., Zhou, L., Xue, X., & Zhou, Y. (2023). The risk impacts of global natural and technological disasters. *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, 88, 101653. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seps.2023.101653>

³⁸ Gilder, A. (2022). Human security. In: O. Richmond & G. Visoka (Eds.), *The Palgrave Encyclopedia of Peace and Conflict Studies*. (pp. 494–503). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-11795-5_191-1

³⁹ Krause, K. (2013). Critical perspectives on human security. In: M. Martin & T. Owen (Eds.), *Routledge Handbook of Human Security*. (pp. 76–93). Routledge. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781315885926-8/critical-perspectives-human-security-keith-krause?context=ubx&refId=7c8656da-9c29-470e-a486-48d1870777bb>

⁴⁰ UN Women (2022). *Comparing military and human security spending: Key findings and methodological notes*. Retrieved from <https://www.unwomen.org/sites/default/files/2022-08/Comparing-military-and-human-security-spending-en.pdf>

⁴¹ Birch, M. (2024). Whatever happened to human security? Selective redefining by NATO after thirty years of backsliding. *Medicine, Conflict and Survival*, 40(3), 215–218. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13623699.2024.2387958>

⁴² Heard, K., Paille, P., & Thue, K. (2022). *Human security and the 2022 NATO Strategic Concept: Knowledge, insights and lessons learnt*. RAND Corporation.

these priorities into all phases of operations, in order to protect populations in crisis and prevent risks to the most vulnerable^{43, 44}.

Materials and methods

The retrospective approach allows us to trace the evolution of the concept of “human security” from the post-bipolar period to the conditions of hybrid wars of the twenty-first century. The comparative analysis is used to compare the “narrow” approach focused on protection from physical violence and the “broad” value-based approach to the interpretation of the concept of “human security”, as well as to critically reflect on the realistic reservations about the practical effectiveness of this paradigm. The dialectical understanding of the interrelationships of social phenomena became the basis for analyzing the dynamics of hybrid threats that combine military, information, economic and humanitarian aspects, and contributed to a better understanding of the nature of modern peace as a process rather than a static category.

The systemic approach made it possible to structure the main components of human security in a hybrid peace landscape, proposing a “pyramidal model” of its construction, where basic needs and protection of rights are the basis, and dignity, solidarity and social trust form the top.

The philosophical vision of the study is formed within the framework of “social constructivism”, according to which knowledge and security perceptions do not reflect the world “as it is”, but are constructed through discourses, practices and interactions of actors. Thus, security is viewed as a product of social construction, depending on interpretations, context and the changing nature of threats. This allows us to integrate a critical perspective and take into account the human dimension of security – taking into account not only structural but also symbolic and emotional and psychological factors.

⁴³ NATO (2024). Human security. North Atlantic Treaty Organization. https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_181779.htm

⁴⁴ NATO (2025). The Secretary General's Annual Report – 2024. https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/2025/4/pdf/sgar24-en.pdf

2: THE EVOLUTION OF THE CONCEPT OF HUMAN SECURITY IN THE CONTEXT OF HYBRID THREATS AND GLOBAL INSTABILITY

Since the end of the Cold War, empirical research has become the basis for the development of the concept of human security. Numerous cases of states turning into insecure actors that neglect their responsibilities to citizens and endanger their existence have undermined respect for sovereignty. Between 2015 and 2023, the global picture of armed conflicts has undergone significant changes, in particular due to the growing number of internal clashes, the emergence of new forms of hybrid confrontation, and the growing humanitarian consequences. According to the leading databases of armed conflicts^{45, 46}, the number of active conflicts in the world increased from 54 in 2015 to 80 in 2023 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of changes in the number of natural and man-made disasters in the world

Source: EM-DAT⁴⁷, CREDUCL⁴⁸

⁴⁵ EM-DAT (2024). EM-DAT: the Emergency Events Database EM-DAT – The international disaster database. <https://www.emdat.be/>

⁴⁶ CREDUCL (2024). 2024 Disasters in Numbers – World. *ReliefWeb*. https://files.emdat.be/reports/2024_EMDAT_report.pdf

⁴⁷ EM-DAT (2024). *Id.*

On the eve of Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine, the number of people killed in armed conflicts around the world in 2021 increased by 45% compared to the previous year, exceeding the 100,000 mark. Particularly intense outbreaks of violence were recorded in Mali, Ethiopia, Myanmar, and eastern Ukraine. As a result, 2022 went down in history as the bloodiest year since the 1994 Rwandan genocide, and was also recognized as the worst year in the history of the Global Peace Index^{49, 50}.

Growing geopolitical competition is fueling conflicts in many countries. Large and medium-sized powers struggle for influence in states or regions, supporting competing interests by supplying troops and weapons. Drones have also emerged as a key weapon and have played an important role in several wars, with military and commercial drones being used extensively in Ethiopia, Ukraine, and Myanmar. The total number of drone attacks increased by 40.8% in 2022, while the number of groups using drones increased by 24%⁵¹.

Analysing the interdisciplinary linkages between security sectors provides the broader perspective needed to identify priorities in a changing risk environment. Such a perspective allows us to focus not only on protecting against threats, but also on creating conditions for a dignified, just and sustainable life, taking into account social, cultural, environmental and political factors⁵². According to a number of researchers, human security should not be limited to formal institutions or rigid sectoral frameworks; it requires flexibility, sensitivity to context, and constant adaptation to new forms of insecurity^{53, 54}.

In modern industrialized countries, the threat of open military aggression has lost its dominant position in the public discourse of fear. Instead, the primacy has shifted to such phenomena as transnational organized crime, terrorist acts, and the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction, in particular by rogue states or non-state actors supporting extremism. These fears are often superimposed on debates about immigration and border control, although the latter have in fact had limited impact on preventing new asymmetric threats.

⁴⁸ CREDUCL (2024). *Id.*

⁴⁹ IEP (2023). *Global Peace Index 2023*. Institute for Economics & Peace. *Global Peace Index 2023: Measuring Peace in a Complex World*, Sydney. <https://www.visionofhumanity.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/GPI-2023-Web.pdf>

⁵⁰ Vision of Humanity (2023a). *Conflict Trends in 2023: A Growing Threat to Global Peace*. <https://www.visionofhumanity.org/conflict-trends-in-2023-a-growing-threat-to-global-peace/>

⁵¹ Vision of Humanity (2023b). *Global Peace Index, 2023*. Retrieved from <https://www.visionofhumanity.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/GPI-2023-Web.pdf>

⁵² Kaldor, M. (2006). *Human Security: A Relevant Concept? Politique étrangère, 4*, 1–16.

⁵³ Krause, K. (2013). *Id.*

⁵⁴ Estrada-Tanck, D. (2016). *Id.*

According to the approach proposed by Mary Kaldor⁵⁵, these challenges are elements of “new wars” – conflicts that combine features of traditional armed confrontations, human rights violations and elements of a criminalized economy. In such wars, the boundaries between military and civilians, internal and external, state and non-state are blurred. Their solution requires not only military tools, but above all a comprehensive political and social approach aimed at reconciliation, restoration of justice, human security and long-term resilience of communities.

Thus, human security in the modern world should be not only a value orientation, but also a practical analytical tool capable of identifying structural imbalances, social vulnerabilities and new configurations of threats that determine the nature of the global order of the twenty-first century.

The United Nations Charter of 1945 laid the foundations for the modern vision of security, emphasizing the multiplicity of fundamental values and their deep interconnection with various forms of threats. The humanistic ideals that defined the 1940s, such as “freedom from fear”, “freedom from poverty” and “respect for human dignity”, became a kind of moral and value-based guideline in the postwar world⁵⁶.

After the end of the Cold War, these basic ideas were rethought in the new historical circumstances, which led to the formation of the concept of human security in the 1990s. It was during this period that the public and academic discourse returned to the rhetoric of the 1940s, where concepts such as freedom from fear and want emerged as the ethical core of the new security paradigm. The idea that “freedom from violence” is a prerequisite for a “decent life” has become a central principle in attempts to reorient security toward the human person⁵⁷.

To specify and analytically implement these principles, the United Nations Development Programme in the 1994 Global Human Development Report (HDR) proposed seven dimensions of human security: economic, food, health, environmental, personal, social and political⁵⁸. These categories were intended as an instrumental list of key values for identifying relevant threats in the context of real social situations. However, the Report itself recognized that such a division is conditional: the dimensions significantly overlap, complement each other and do not cover all aspects of vital human needs. In fact, most modern threats do not lend themselves to strict division – they affect several areas of life simultaneously. For example, an armed conflict can simultaneously destroy medical infrastructure, violate human rights, undermine political stability and environmental security. Thus, none of the proposed dimensions can be considered in isolation from the others without losing the integrity of the analysis.

⁵⁵ Kaldor, M. (2006). *Id.*

⁵⁶ UN (1945). Charter of the United Nations and Statute of the International Court of Justice. <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/un-charter>

⁵⁷ Alkire, S. (2003). *A conceptual framework for human security*. Working Paper. Queen Elizabeth House, University of Oxford.

⁵⁸ UNDP (1994). *Human Development Report 1994: New Dimensions of Human Security*. Oxford University Press. pp. 24-25.

Moreover, the 1994 Report made it clear that the proposed framework does not claim to be an exhaustive or universal framework for conceptualizing human security. On the contrary, it aims to stimulate a context-oriented approach in which flexibility of thinking and interdisciplinarity are key tools for determining priorities in responding to dynamic threats⁵⁹.

Thus, the transformation of security thinking from state-centric to people-centric models is not only a consequence of historical circumstances, but also a reflection of a deeper understanding of the complex nature of human vulnerability in the context of globalization and post-industrial development.

3: RETHINKING HUMAN SECURITY: AT THE INTERSECTION OF SOCIAL, ENVIRONMENTAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL DIMENSIONS

The issue of human security in the 21st century has become particularly relevant due to the growth of global risks, hybrid threats and the blurring of traditional boundaries between internal and external security factors^{60, 61}. Despite attempts to systematize this category in UN reports, in particular in the Human Development Report⁶², a number of concepts, including “personal security” or “community security”, have remained vaguely defined and have not been integrated into policy portfolios^{63, 64}.

Personal security encompasses a wide range of threats, from violence and crime to accidents, substance abuse or negligence, making it difficult to attribute it to a specific policy sector⁶⁵. Community security remains politically controversial, particularly in the context of intergroup conflict, ethnic tensions or discrimination against indigenous peoples.

Despite the existence of seven main categories of human security outlined in 1994 (personal, economic, political, food, environmental, public, health security), only a few of them have received practical and scientific recognition. For example, in the Routledge Handbook of Human Security⁶⁶, the term “human security” is mentioned more than 2400 times, while “personal security” is mentioned only three times and “community security” is mentioned twice. “National security” (136 times) or “state

⁵⁹ UNDP (1994). *Id.*

⁶⁰ UNDP (1994). *Id.*

⁶¹ Alkire, S. (2003). *Id.*

⁶² UNDP (1994). *Id.*

⁶³ Martin, M., & Owen, T. (Eds.). (2013). *Routledge handbook of human security*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315885926>

⁶⁴ Sachs, J. D., Lafortune, G., & Fuller, G. (2024). *The SDGs and the UN Summit of the Future. Sustainable Development Report 2024*. Dublin University Press. <https://www.dublinuniversitypress.com/the-sdgs-and-the-un-summit-of-the-future>

⁶⁵ Alkire, S. (2003). *Id.*

⁶⁶ Martin, M., & Owen, T. (Eds.). (2013). *Id.*

security” (33 times) are much more common, which indicates the dominance of the traditional state-centric approach to understanding security.

In a hybrid world where aggression has not only a military but also a socio-technological dimension, new forms of threats necessitate a rethinking of human security as a holistic system that encompasses both physical survival and dignity, social well-being and resilience to information manipulation⁶⁷. Hybrid technologies are increasingly aimed at destabilizing society through terrorophobia, emotional manipulation, and the undermining of trust, which replaces the natural course of social development with adventurous political scenarios. As Alkire⁶⁸ notes, human security involves preserving a vital core – a minimum set of conditions for survival, livelihoods, and dignity. At the same time, the understanding of security must be adapted to the local context and cultural specificity, taking into account social vulnerability, imbalances in rights, and access to resources. This is extremely important for countries in a state of protracted conflicts or under the influence of external aggression, such as Ukraine, where human security is inseparable from issues of national security, preservation of statehood, social cohesion and mental health of citizens^{69, 70, 71}. Thus, modern challenges require an update of the human security paradigm, which must be flexible, interdisciplinary and able to respond to the dynamics of risks in the hybrid world.

Analysis of the qualitative state of human potential in countries engulfed in war, in particular in Ukraine, testifies to a critical deterioration in the moral and psychological state of the civilian population and forms pessimistic forecasts for further social development. The insufficient attention previously paid to the formation of a system of vital human security turned out to be a strategic mistake. It is not only about health care as an institutional function, but also about creating conditions for mental balance, harmonious development and ensuring a subjective sense of security, which is the basis of psychological well-being⁷².

The reductionist approach to health care, focused mainly on responding to consequences, rather than prevention, has led not only to physical losses during armed conflicts, but also to a deep erosion of public trust in state security institutions⁷³. This is

⁶⁷ Ahmadzai, A. (2020). *Id.*

⁶⁸ Alkire, S. (2003). *Id.*

⁶⁹ Khan, F., Muhabullah, M., Islam, R., & Khan, M. (2021). A cost-effective autonomous air defence system for national security. *Security and Communication Network*, 2021, 9984453. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/9984453>

⁷⁰ Fact (2024, 23 May). *The impact of war on the mental health of adults and children: analysis after more than two years of hostilities in Ukraine (part 1)*. <https://fact-news.com.ua/vpliv-viyni-napsihichne-zdorov-ya-doroslih-i-ditey-analiz-cherez-ponad-dva-roki-viyskovih-diy-v-ukraini-chastina-1/>

⁷¹ Gradus Research Plus (2024). *Mental health and attitudes of Ukrainians towards psychological assistance during the war*. <https://gradus.app/en/open-reports/mental-health-and-attitudes-ukrainians-towards-psychological-assistance-during-war/>

⁷² Alkire, S. (2003). *Id.*

⁷³ Gowan, R. (2024). Trends in armed conflicts. *SIPRI*. Retrieved from <https://www.sipri.org/yearbook/2024/02>

especially noticeable in regions that have experienced both occupation and liberation. Citizens who have suffered from large-scale aggression and terrorist acts have the right to expect the state to create a reliable security model that guarantees not only physical but also psychological protection, prevents manipulative influence on consciousness, and forms an adaptive environment⁷⁴.

Similar risks can be observed in Syria, which has been in a state of armed conflict since 2011. According to the UN⁷⁵, the humanitarian situation in the country is critical: 16.7 million people need assistance, which is more than 75% of the population. The continuation of hostilities, air strikes on Damascus, Homs provinces and rural areas have led to mass casualties among the civilian population, damage to infrastructure and millions of internally displaced persons. The attacks in January 2024 led to the shutdown of hundreds of critical infrastructure facilities: water supply, medical centers, schools, leaving more than a million people without electricity. This has exacerbated the food crisis, malnutrition and increased vulnerability among children, pregnant women and nursing mothers⁷⁶.

One often underestimated aspect of human security is the environmental dimension. The cost of environmental degradation and depletion of natural resources in the context of war is rarely taken into account as part of the “human cost” of conflict. Daoudi⁷⁷ emphasizes that under the new security paradigm, the environment is no longer seen as a freely available resource that can be exploited, but as a determining variable that directly affects the viability of society.

Thus, the experience of Ukraine and Syria demonstrates the need to rethink the concept of human security as a comprehensive system that combines the physical, psychological, social and environmental dimensions. Based on the research conducted, key security areas that require priority attention were identified (Figure 2).

⁷⁴ Ahmadzai, A. (2020). *Id.*

⁷⁵ UN (2024, 27 February). *As Syria's humanitarian crisis worsens, Security Council delegates stress need for Damascus to re-engage with constitutional committee.* <https://press.un.org/en/2024/sc15602.doc.htm>

⁷⁶ UN (2024, 27 February). *Id.*

⁷⁷ Daoudi, M. (2020, 14 December). *Syria's human security is inseparable from its environmental health.* *The Century Foundation.* Retrieved from <https://tcf.org/content/report/syrias-human-security-inseparable-environmental-health/>

Figure 2. Fundamental components of vital security
Source: developed by the authors

The need to form a renewed paradigm of vital security becomes obvious in the context of hybrid threats and instability.

4: THE HYBRID WORLD AND THE TRANSFORMATION OF THE HUMAN SECURITY PARADIGM

Nowadays, it is becoming increasingly relevant among scholars to consider security challenges within the framework of the hybridity paradigm, which encompasses not only armed conflicts, but also peace-making processes. The concept of hybrid peace⁷⁸ goes beyond traditional ideas about liberal peace, proposing a dynamic model of interaction between global and local security factors, which encompasses different levels of power, social and cultural influences.

Critics of the liberal paradigm draw attention to a number of fundamental limitations of this approach. In particular, it is emphasized that liberal peace is often presented as a universal and neutral mechanism, but in practice it is based on secularized values that can conflict with local norms and expectations⁷⁹. This approach

⁷⁸ Anam, S. (2018). Peacebuilding: The shift towards a hybrid peace approach. *Jurnal Global & Strategis*, 9(1), 37–48. <https://doi.org/10.20473/jgs.9.1.2015.37-48>

⁷⁹ MacGinty, R. (2010). Hybrid peace: The interaction between top-down and bottom-up peace. *Security Dialogue*, 41(4), 391–412. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0967010610374312>

emphasizes the priority of rights over needs, ignores deep social inequalities and focuses on territorial sovereignty, often neglecting social justice. Critics also point out that the proposed “incentives” or rewards within the liberal strategy are asymmetric and inaccessible to vulnerable groups, which deprives these approaches of their emancipatory potential.

At the same time, defenders of liberal internationalism emphasize its pragmatic role in achieving the Millennium Development Goals: security, stability, good governance and strengthening of state institutions are seen as prerequisites for the provision of public goods, in particular in education, health care and poverty alleviation. At the same time, modern interpretations of liberal peace increasingly focus on a partnership discourse, within which local communities are not perceived as passive recipients of aid, but as full-fledged cooperative subjects capable of influencing the formation of policies and security decisions⁸⁰.

Hybrid peace appears as a variable, multi-level and interdependent system in which stable hierarchies are absent. Instead of a clear pattern of dominance, we are dealing with a pluralism of influences: at different times, on different issues and in different regions, different forces can prevail – global, regional or local. Western political, military and humanitarian structures, although equipped with a powerful monitoring system, are often unable to identify subtle local signals of resistance or transformational dynamics that do not fit into their information templates. The reason for this is the lack of cultural sensitivity and anthropological knowledge, which are necessary to understand the complex social fabric of host communities. A key factor in the formation of sustainable peace in conditions of hybridity is the recognition of the role of local agents who are able to offer alternative models of reconciliation, based on customary law, cultural traditions and informal mechanisms for conflict resolution. Many postcolonial societies retain their own deeply rooted institutions for resolving conflicts that are no less effective than the “universal” tools offered by the global community⁸¹.

Thus, the hybrid world should not be seen as the result of the hybridization of a separate existing liberal peace – on the contrary, the liberal world itself, from the moment of its incarnation, has always been woven into a context of hybridity, which changes its shape, boundaries and meaning. It is not simply the sum of conflicting models, but a dynamic field of interaction of diverse rationalities, interests and norms. The conceptualization of the hybrid order is an attempt to describe how new forms of peace are formed in different spatio-temporal contexts, emerging from the constant interaction of the local and the global.

Given the above, vital security in conditions of hybridity cannot be defined through fixed and unified categories. It is more appropriate to present it as a flexible multi-level structure, similar to a pyramid, reminiscent of Maslow's model. However, unlike the classical hierarchy of needs, such a pyramid is dynamic and variable, its levels can change places, be integrated or detailed according to a specific socio-cultural

⁸⁰ MacGinty, R. (2010). *Id.*

⁸¹ MacGinty, R. (2010). *Id.*

context. This forms an adaptive security matrix that is able to respond to the changing challenges of a hybrid environment.

Traditional approaches to security have been dominated by the thesis that the state is the main referent of security. However, the events after the terrorist attacks of September 11, 2001 and the subsequent anti-terrorist campaigns have revealed a paradox: even the most powerful states are vulnerable, and security measures themselves can lead to new threats⁸². Traditional paradigms emphasize that only the state is able to provide systemic and long-term security, even in a world of increasing civil society and NGOs.

In contrast, the concept of vital security puts the person as the central subject, where the state and social institutions perform a supporting and sometimes destructive function. This is especially relevant in conditions of martial law, when citizens find themselves in a situation of social alienation, losing guarantees of rights and freedoms due to the state's focus on preserving territories and geopolitical stability.

Figure 3. The Adaptive Human Security Model: A Pyramidal Perspective
Source: developed by the authors

Defining the person as a security referent means giving him an active role in neutralizing threats. For example, if health care is the responsibility of the state, but its mechanisms are ineffective, it is necessary to create self-protection or compensation systems. This is a new paradigm – viable security, which ensures the ability of the individual as a systemic element of society to adapt to threats caused by the gap

⁸² Kaldor, M. (2006). *Id.*

between public consciousness and the effectiveness of social management systems. Viable security has a multi-level structure (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Conceptual model of life security

Source: developed by the authors

This structure forms the subject area of vital security as a dynamic social process. Each component includes a network of subjects with their own ideas about the essence and priorities of security.

Vital security – the practical ability of a person to resist external threats – is a key aspect of vital security. In a hybrid world, the degrees of hybridization of social processes, actors and networks vary, forming cultural hierarchies that resist centralization. In such conditions, excessive strengthening of the state without taking into account the local context can lead to the loss of subjectivity of communities.

The hybrid world model offers a different perspective: vital security is considered as a tool for responding to environmental, social and informational challenges. The survival logic underlying this concept focuses on preserving self-identity in conditions of multi-level manipulative pressure. Accordingly, the term “vital potential” is interpreted as the ability not only to survive, but also to function harmoniously in a changing environment, that is, it is the semantic core of the concept of vital security.

CONCLUSION

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The study of vital security naturally follows from the modern concept of human security, which is the subject of extensive academic and institutional analysis. Despite numerous political implications, critical remarks and challenges, this concept remains ambiguous due to the vagueness of its epistemology of threats. The existing realism and neorealism in the liberal scientific debate do not sufficiently reflect the complexity of the hybrid era of the last three decades, which indicates the need to revise the human security paradigm, especially in the aspects of psychological and social protection.

The proposed LEGO model of the vital security “pyramid” is an attempt to conceptualize this complex security in the context of hybridity, demonstrating its flexibility and the interconnectedness of its components.

In addition, the transformation of human security into the foundation of international cooperation responds to contemporary discussions on the integration of security and sustainable development, as well as calls for a more coordinated, effective and efficient system of global cooperation.

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